
E-COMMERCE- BUSINESS- TECHNOLOGY- SOCIETY

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Abstract:

E-Commerce the use of the Internet and the web to transact business. E-Commerce on digitally enabled commercial transactions between and among organizations and individuals. Digitally enabled transactions include all transactions mediated by digital technology. This means transactions that occur over the Internet and the web. Commercial transactions involve the exchange of value across organizational or individual boundaries in return for products and services. Exchange of value is important for understanding the limits of e-commerce without an exchange of value no commerce occurs. This paper identifies the Business, technological and society forces that have shaped the growth of e-commerce.

Keywords: *E-Commerce; Digital; Commercial; Society.*

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1. Introduction

The Difference between E-commerce and E-business

E-Commerce

E-Commerce encompasses the entire world of electronically based organizational activities that support a firm's market exchanges including a firm's entire information system's infrastructure.

E-Business

E-Business refer to digital enabling of transactions and processes within a firm involving information system under the control of the firm. E-Business does not include commercial transactions involving an exchange of value across organizational boundaries.

Types of E-Commerce

- Business to Consumer (B2C)
- Business to Business (B2B)
- Consumer to Consumer (C2C)
- Peer to Peer (P2P)
- Mobile Commerce

Business to Consumer (B2C)

Business to Consumer (B2C) in which online businesses attempt to reach individual consumers. This type of e-commerce that most consumers are likely to encounter. There are seven different Business to Consumer (B2C) business models are Online retailers, Content providers, Transaction brokers, Service providers, and Community providers.

Business to Business (B2B)

Business to Business (B2B) e-commerce in which businesses focus on selling to other businesses is the largest form of e-commerce. There are two primary business models used within the Business to Business (B2B) area: Net market places, which includes e-distributors, e-procurement companies, exchanges and industry consortia and private industrial networks which include single firm networks and industry-wide networks.

Consumer to Consumer (C2C)

Consumer to Consumer (C2C) provides a way for consumers to sell to each other, with the help of an online market maker such as the action site eBay. Consumer to Consumer (C2C) e-commerce, the consumer prepares the product for market, places the product for auction or sale so that product can be easily displayed, discovered and paid for.

Peer to Peer

P2P E-commerce enables internet users to share files and computer resources directly without having to go through a central web server. P2P form no intermediary is required. P2P networks make use of intermediary “Super Servers” to speed operations.

Mobile Commerce (M-Commerce)

M-Commerce refers to the use of wireless digital devices to enable transactions on the web. M-Commerce involves the use wireless networks to connect cell phones, handheld devices and personal computers to the web.

2. E-Commerce Business models

- Business model is a set of planned activities designed to result in a profit in a market Place. It’s at the center of the business Plan. Business Plan is a document that describes a firm’s business model.

EIGHT KEY ELEMENTS OF A BUSINESS MODEL

KEY ELEMENTS OF A BUSINESS MODEL	
COMPONENTS	KEY QUESTIONS
Value proposition	Why should the customer buy from you?
Revenue model	
Market opportunity	How will you earn money?
Competitive environment	What marketplace do you intend to serve, and what is its size?
Competitive advantage	Who else occupies your intended marketplace?
Market strategy	What special advantages does your firm bring to the marketplace?
Organizational development	How do you plan to promote your products or services to attract your target audience?
Management team	What types of organizational structures within the firm are necessary to carry out the business plan? What kinds of experiences and background are important for the company’s leaders to have?

B2C BUSINESS MODEL

B2C BUSINESS MODELS				
BUSINESS MODEL	VARIATIONS	EXAMPLES	DESCRIPTION	REVENUE MODEL
Portal	Horizontal/General	Yahoo AOL MSN	Offers an integrated package of content and content – search, services news, e-mail, chat, and music downloads, video streaming, calendars, etc. Seeks to be a user’s home base	Advertising, subscription fees, transaction fees
	Vertical/Specialized (Vortal) Search	Sailnet	Offers services and products to specialized marketplace	Same
		Google Ask.com	Focuses primarily on offering search services	Advertising, affiliate referral
	Virtual Merchant	Amazon	Online version of retail store, where customers can shop at any hour of the day or night without leaving their home or office	Sales of goods
	Bricks-and-clicks	Walmart.com Sears.com	Online distribution channel for a company that also has physical stores	Same
	Catalog Merchant	LLBean.com Lilliant Vernon.com	Online version of direct mail catalog	Same
	Manufacturer-direct	Dell.com Mattel.com Sony.com	Manufacturer uses online channel to sell direct to customer	Same
Content Provider		WSJ.com Sportline.com CNN.com ESPN.com Real Rhapsody	Information and entertainment providers such as newspapers, sports sites, and other online sources that offer customers up-to-date news and special interest how-to guidance and tips and/or information sales	Advertising, Subscription fees, affiliate referral fees
Market Creator		eBay Priceline	Web-based businesses that use Internet technology to create markets that bring buyers and sellers together	Transaction fees
Service provider		VisaNow.com xDrive.com myCFO.com BlueFlag.com	Companies that make money by selling users a service, rather than a product	Sales of services

Community Provider	iVillage Friendster MySpace Facebook About.com	Sites where individuals with particular interests, hobbies, common experiences, or social networks can come together and “meet” online	Advertising. Subscription. affiliate referral fees
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B2B BUSINESS MODEL

B2B BUSINESS MODELS			
BUSINESS MODEL	EXAMPLES	DESCRIPTION	REVENUE MODEL
<i>1) NET MARKETPLACE</i>			
E.distributor	Grainger.com Partstore.com	Single-firm online version of retail and wholesale store; supply maintenance, repair, operation goods; indirect inputs	Sales of goods
E.procurement	Ariba Perfect commerce	Single firm creating digital markets where sellers and buyers transact for indirect inputs	Fees for market-making services; supply chain management, and fulfillment services Fees and commissions on transactions
Exchange Consortium	Farms.com Foodtrader	Independently owned vertical digital marketplace for direct inputs	Fees and commissions on transactions
Industry Consortium	Elemica Exostar Quadrem	Industry-owned vertical digital market open to select suppliers	Fees and commissions on transactions
<i>2) PRIVATE INDUSTRIAL NETWORK</i>			
Single firm	Wal-Mart Proctor & Gamble	Company-owned network to coordinate supply chains with a limited set of partners	Cost absorbed by network owner and recovered through production and distribution efficiencies
Industry-wide	1 SYNC Agentrics	Industry-owned network to set standards, coordinate supply and logistics for the industry	Contributions from industry member firms and recovered through production and distribution efficiencies; fees

for transactions
and services.

**CONSUMER – TO – CONSUMER (C2C) BUSINESS MODELS
BUSINESS MODELS IN EMERGING E-COMMERCE AREAS**

BUSINESS	EXAMPLES	DESCRIPTION	REVENUE MODEL
Consumer – to – consumer	eBay Half – com	Helps consumers connect with other consumers to conduct business	Transaction fees
Peer – to – peer	Kazaa Cloudmark	Technology enabling consumers to share files and services via the Web, without a common server	Subscription fees, advertising transaction fees
M-commerce	eBay Anywhere PayPal Mobile Checkout AOL Moviefone	Extending business applications using wireless technology	Sales of goods and services

3. E-Commerce Technology

System analysis, Business objectives, System functionality and Information Requirement

SYSTEM ANALYSIS: BUSINESS OBJECTIVES, SYSTEM FUNCTIONALITY, AND INFORMATION REQUIREMENTS FOR A TYPICAL E-COMMERCE SITE		
BUSINESS OBJECTIVE	SYSTEM FUNCTIONALITY	INFORMATION REQUIREMENT
Display goods	Digital catalog	Dynamic text and graphics catalog
Provide product information (content)	Product database	description, stocking number, inventory levels
Personalize/Customize product Customer on-site tracking Site log for every customer visit.	data mining capability to identify	customer paths and appropriate responses
Execute a transaction payment system	Shopping cart/payment	Secure credit card clearing; multiple options
Accumulate customer information registration	Customer database	Name, address, Phone, and e-mail for all customers; online customer
Provide after-sale customer support	Sales database	Customer ID, product, date, payment, Shipment date

Coordinate marketing/advertising/banner	Ad server, e-mail server, e-mail, campaign manager, ad banner manager	Site behavior log of prospects and customers linked to e-mail and ad campaigns.
Understand marketing effectiveness	Site tracking and reporting system	Number of unique visitors, pages visited, products purchased, identified by marketing campaign
Provide production and supplier links inventory levels, supplier	Inventory management system	Product and ID and contact, order quantity data by product

THE EIGHT MOST IMPORTANT FACTORS IN SUCCESSFUL E-COMMERCE SITE DESIGN	
FACTOR	DESCRIPTION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functionality • Informational • Ease of use • Redundant navigation • Ease of purchase • Multi-browser functionality • Simple graphics • Legible text 	<p>Pages that works, load quickly, and point the customer your product offerings</p> <p>Links that customers can easily find to discover more about you and your products</p> <p>Simple fool-proof navigation</p> <p>Alternative navigation to the same content</p> <p>One or two clicks to purchase</p> <p>Site works with the most popular browsers</p> <p>Avoids distracting, obnoxious graphics and sounds that the user cannot control</p> <p>Avoids backgrounds that distort text or make it illegible</p>

4. Ecommerce Social Issues

The Internet and its use in e-commerce have raised pervasive ethical, social, and political issues on a scale unprecedented for computer technology.

UNIQUE FEATURES OF E-COMMERCE TECHNOLOGY AND THEIR POTENTIAL ETHICAL, SOCIAL, AND/OR POLITICAL IMPLICATIONS	
E-COMMERCE TECHNOLOGY	POTENTIAL ETHICAL, SOCIAL, AND POLITICAL SIGNIFICANCE
Ubiquity – Internet/Web technology is available everywhere: at work, at home, and elsewhere via mobile devices, anytime	Work and shopping can invade family life; shopping can distract workers at work, lowering productivity; use of mobile devices can lead to automobile and industrial accidents, Presents confusing issues of “nexus” to taxation authorities.
E-COMMERCE TECHNOLOGY	POTENTIAL ETHICAL, SOCIAL, AND POLITICAL SIGNIFICANCE
Global reach – The technology reaches across national boundaries, around the Earth	Reduces cultural diversity in products; weakens local small firms while strengthening large global firms; moves manufacturing production to low-wage area of the world; weakens the ability of all nations – large and small-to control their information destiny.
Universal standards – There is one set of technology standards, namely Internet standards	Increases vulnerability to viruses and hacking attacks worldwide affecting millions of people at once. Increases the likelihood of “information” crime, crimes against systems, and deception.
Richness –Video, audio, and text messages are possible.	A “screen technology” that reduces use of text and potentially the ability to read by focusing instead on video and audio messages. Potentially very persuasive messages possible that may reduce reliance on multiple independent sources of information.
Interactivity – The technology works through interaction with the user.	The nature of interactivity at commercial sites can be shallow and meaningless. Customer e-mails are frequently not read by human beings. Customers do not really “co-produce” the product as much as they “co-produce” the sale. The amount of “customization” of products that occurs is minimal, occurring within predefined platforms and plug-in options.
Information density – The technology reduces information costs, raises quality.	While the total amount of information available to all parties increases, so does the possibility of false and misleading information, unwanted information, and invasion of solitude. Trust, authenticity, accuracy, completeness, and other quality features of information can be degraded. The ability of individuals and organizations to make sense of out of this plethora of information is limited.

Personalization/Customization- The technology allows personalized messages to be delivered to individuals as well as groups.	Opens up the possibility of intensive invasion of privacy for commercial and governmental purposes that is unprecedented.
Social technology – The technology enables user content generation and social networking.	Creates opportunities for cyber bullying, abusive language, and predation; challenges concepts of privacy, fair use, and consent to use posted information; creates new opportunities for surveillance by authorities and corporations into private lives.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we study about E-commerce in business model, technology, society issues. The technology provides the infrastructure, it is the business applications. To understand some key business concept such as electronic markets, information goods. The primary societal issues are intellectual property, individual privacy and public policy. So the study of this e-commerce will be helpful to understand technology, business, society and its various application areas and models.

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